

The Impact of Perceived Service Quality on Students' Intentions in Higher Education of Private Colleges and Universities in Myanmar

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Abstract

This study research to investigate the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar. In terms of method, groups of private colleges and universities are selected among 50 private colleges and universities in Myanmar, 7 Selected Private Colleges and Universities and then a random sample of 602 students is selected from the target student list by using the two-stage sampling method. The study used primary data collected through the use of survey questionnaires. This study indicated that reliability, tangibility, responsiveness, empathy, and assurance are positively and significantly affected by students' intentions at the 1% level of significance. This study also found that between service quality and students' intentions. It is expected that key findings, especially the proposed model, will help in supporting Myanmar government policy initiatives, especially to increase higher education service quality as part of the educational institutions'. The evidence shows a link among service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar.

Keywords: service quality, students' intentions, higher education, colleges & universities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive academic environment, education institutions must focus on attracting and retaining students to maintain a competitive advantage of private higher education in Myanmar. They must develop effective strategies to attract and retain students, focusing on student satisfaction and creating conducive learning environments to ensure academic success.

The private higher education is struggling with the difficult issue of student retention. The number of qualified students who stay in higher education institutions, effective student retention measures must be put into place (Lau, 2003). Customers who receive high-quality service are more likely to stay with the business and recommend it to others (Negi, 2009; Ladhari, 2009). In order to evaluate service quality for research purposes, the relationship between service quality and customer behavioral outcomes has drawn a lot of attention. According to DeShields et al (2005), In order to succeed in a cutthroat service environment, higher education institutions, must maintain high standards of service quality and students' intentions.

Organizations must prioritize customer satisfaction and service quality in their external relationships to maintain competitiveness. Service quality is a key factor in gaining a competitive edge. For service offerings to stand out, add value, and gain a strategic competitive advantage, service quality is essential. Intense competitions nowadays have focused on results such as research and innovation for society. That is why institutions have been expected to provide

high service quality. In order to maintain a sustainable competitive advantage in the current global educational market, institutions must satisfy their students by offering excellent service values. (Huang et al., 2012).

The study is to investigate the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar.

2. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

In today's competitive education market, universities strive for excellent service quality to build student relationships and market position. However, immoral business practices and poor service quality can negatively impact behavioral intention and customer satisfaction.

Service quality affects consumer attitudes and behavior across various industries, many researchers and practitioners today change the service quality components. The ability of service providers to successfully implement concrete, trustworthy, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy in carrying out daily tasks may have a significant impact on positive customer cognitive and attitude reactions, particularly customer satisfaction, according to research on effective organizations. (Izogo and Ogba, 2015; Yeo et al. 2015).

This research shows that excellent customer service leads to loyalty. Service providers must understand the connection between service quality and customer satisfaction to prioritize satisfaction or deliver the highest perceived quality. This study's main goal is to the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are

1. To examine the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar.
2. To identify the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar.
3. To determine the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar.

4. METHOD OF STUDY

This study employs survey research methodology and a deductive approach. In this study, a basic random sampling technique will be applied. Examine quantitative data from 50 Private College and Universities, choosing a 7 Selected a random sample of 602 students. Structured questionnaires with Google Forms will be used to gather the data. This study will be a descriptive investigation. This study only examined the variables the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar. The cluster sampling method will be applied, and an arbitrary sample of internet users will be selected. Data from both primary and secondary sources will be used in this study. Each item is rated using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree. A score of four is regarded as neutral.

5. POPULATION AND SAMPLING

This study only focuses on the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar. The study applied Cognitive-Affective-Behavioral Model, Planned Behavior Theory, and SERVQUAL Model. Tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy perspectives are studied to measure service quality. Some variables that relate to service quality are excluded. Moreover, there are some limitations, especially in target groups, stakeholders, and participation. Specific attention is paid to students enrolled in the 2022-2023 academic years.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

6.1 Service

According to Johns (1999), although though services are intangible and their results are viewed as activities rather than actual goods, certain service outputs do include some crucial elements, such as real facilities, machinery, and staff. Kotler et al. (1999) identified five essential features that set services apart from products. According to some service providers, a service is an activity that combines aspects of basic delivery, service operation, individualized care, and interpersonal performance that are handled differently in various industries. However, Johns (1999) defined a customer's perspective of service as a life experience that combined fundamental needs, decision-making power, and emotional content.

6.2 SERVQUAL Model

In the marketing literature, SERVQUAL is a crucial tool for assessing the caliber of services (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, 1988). According to Parasuraman et al., managers have used this instrument extensively, (1998) and researchers to gauge how customers feel about the level of service. According to Parasuraman (1988), consumers evaluate the quality of services using the same standards, regardless of the kind. On the other hand, many regard quality as a competitive advantage among educational institutions.

6.3 Service Quality

Previous studies have shown that customers' opinions about a company's overall uniqueness or dominance impact how well they perceive the quality of its offerings (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, 1988). Jiang and Wang (2006) defined it as the customer's assessment of the quality of the service they received and how it compared to their expectations. Jiang and Wang (2006) noted that customers' feelings or memories are used to make judgments rather than the characteristics of the service. Customer satisfaction serves as the basis for evaluating the quality of a service.

6.4 Dimensions of Service Quality

The most famous model of service quality was proposed by Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988). It had five dimensions and can be explained as:

1. Reliability: “the degree to which a promised service is performed dependably and accurately”
2. Responsiveness: “the degree to which service providers are willing to help customers and provide prompt service”.
3. Assurance: “the extent to which service providers are knowledgeable, courteous, and able to inspire trust and confidence”
4. Empathy: “the degree to which the customers are offered caring and individualized attention”.
5. Tangibles: “the degree to which physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel are adequate.

7. Service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities

The service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities are determined by using five factors: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. These factors are analyzed by using five-point Likert scales. Likert-type item scales are expressed with five response alternatives: strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4) and strongly agree (5). In examining the perception on each factor, it is used sentiment score (mean) and standard deviation.

7.1 Perceived service quality on students' intentions of Tangibility

In examining the perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar, it is firstly determined the perception on tangibility. This factor is studied by using five statements. The survey results are shown in below Table 1.

Table 1. Tangibility

No.	Statement	Sentiment Score	Std. Dev
Q1	University campus have complete environment for academic.	3.77	0.88
Q2	Library, teaching and learning Portal have sufficient software and hardware resources.	3.75	0.85
Q3	Teaching equipment are perfection.	3.75	0.86
Q4	Logistic services and related writings are sufficient.	3.80	0.92
Q5	University has positive visibility at the current level and culture life.	3.86	1.00

Figure 1. Students' intentions on Tangibility

Based on survey responses, it is found that most of students have more positive agreement on their university have positive visibility at the current level and culture life, and followed by more positive agreement on sufficient logistic services and related writings of their colleges and universities. And then, it is found that positive agreement on their university campus that have complete environment for their academic. Nevertheless, it is seen that there is less agreement on sufficient software and hardware of library, teaching and learning Portal and perfect teaching equipment than the remaining statements.

7.2 Perceived service quality on students' intentions of Reliability

In examining the perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar, secondly, it is determined the perception on reliability. This factor is studied by using six statements. The survey results are shown in below Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability

No.	Statement	Sentiment Score	Std. Dev
Q1	University campus have high security for academic teaching and learning.	3.93	0.86
Q2	Teaching tasks and classes are held respecting the schedule of lecturers in time.	4.10	0.83
Q3	Willing of the staff to help students dealing with their problems.	3.90	0.95
Q4	Staff of the faculty provides support for students with the expected help.	3.83	1.02
Q5	Academic staff respects lecturers and exam schedules as well as informing students about the schedule changes in advance.	4.21	0.75
Q6	Consistent grading criteria is applied by staff.	3.92	0.91

Figure 2. Students' intentions on Reliability

As the survey data results, it is found that most of students have more positive agreement on respects of academic staffs such as lecturers and exam schedules as well as informing students about the schedule changes in advance and followed by perception on respecting the schedule of lecturers in time for teaching tasks and classes. Moreover, it is found that more positive agreement on high security for academic teaching and learning, consistent grading criteria and willing of the staff to help students dealing with their problems. But students are less agreement on staff of the faculty who provides support for students with the expected help than the remaining statements.

7.2.1 Perceived service quality on students' intentions of Responsiveness

In examining the perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar, thirdly, it is determined the perception on responsiveness. This factor is studied by using five statements. The survey results are shown in below Table 3.

Table 3. Responsiveness

No.	Statement	Sentiment Score	Std. Dev.
Q1	Handling and resolving the students' claims promptly.	3.89	0.95
Q2	Students' best interest is in the focus of academic staff.	4.10	0.80
Q3	Willingness of faculty staff to help students and can handle student matters in a timely manner.	4.02	0.87
Q4	Whether teachers can timely respond to students' learning needs.	4.06	0.87
Q5	The provision status of immediate service by school.	3.81	0.91

Figure 3. Students' intentions on Responsiveness

According to the results of above table, it is found that most of students are more agreed that students' best interest is in the focus of academic staff, and followed by teachers can timely respond to students' learning needs. Moreover, the students are agreement on willingness of faculty staff to help students and can handle student matters in a timely manner and handling and resolving the students' claims promptly. But most of students are less agreement on the provision status of immediate service by school than the remaining statements.

7.2.2 Perceived service quality on students' intentions of Assurance

In examining the perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private business colleges and universities in Myanmar, fourthly, it is determined the perception on assurance. This factor is studied by using five statements. The survey results are shown in below Table 4.

Table 4. Assurance

No.	Statement	Sentiment Score	Std. Dev
Q1	Faculty staff has the necessary knowledge and adequate communication skills.	3.85	0.90
Q2	Study and educational programs are implemented for specialization of the students.	3.97	0.86
Q3	Professional answers are given to students' questions by high level quality of education process.	3.98	0.86
Q4	The behavior of academic staff instilling confidence in students.	3.96	0.92
Q5	The adequate reputation and position of the faculty in the environment.	4.09	0.84

Figure 4 Students' intentions on Assurance

It is found that most of students are more positive agreement on the adequate reputation and position of the faculty in the environment, and followed by professional answers that are given to students' questions by high level quality of education process. And then, the positive agreements are found in the implemented study and educational programs for specialization of the students and the behavior of academic staff instilling confidence in students. Nevertheless, students are less agreement on the necessary knowledge and adequate communication skills of faculty staffs than the remaining statements.

7.2.3 Perceived service quality on students' intentions of Empathy

In examining the perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar, fifthly, it is determined the perception on empathy. This factor is studied by using five statements. The survey results are shown in below Table 5.

Table 5. Empathy

No.	Statement	Sentiment Score	Std. Dev
Q1	Students' needs are well understood by polite and professional academic staff in communication.	3.93	0.91
Q2	Positive attitudes towards students are shown by academic staff.	3.90	0.89
Q3	Students' best interest is the main objective.	4.09	0.83
Q4	Consultations hours are available for students.	3.98	0.91
Q5	Faculty values feedback from students to improve processes.	4.06	0.86

Figure 5. Students' intentions on Empathy

The highest positive agreement is found that students' best interest is the main objective, and followed by perception on faculty values feedback from students to improve processes. And then, students are positive agreement on consultations hours are available for students and students' needs are well understood by polite and professional academic staff in communication. But students are less positive agreement on positive attitudes towards students shown by academic staff.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This research is the impact of perceived service quality on students' intentions in higher education of private colleges and universities in Myanmar. The study is also conducted with purpose of observing the effects of student satisfaction and students' intentions on the linkage between the service quality and behavioral intentions of students. To achieve these aims, the survey was conducted on 602 students from 7 private colleges and universities. The direct relationship between students' intentions and service quality dimensions suggests that providing high-quality services is a crucial survival tactic that boosts both students' intentions and service quality. Therefore, private colleges and universities management regularly evaluates and monitors service quality to identify where improvements are needed from the customer's perspective and to focus on underlying aspects of service quality, particularly the warranty aspect. In general, private college and universities, management departments and management office managers need to keep an eye on changing customer perceptions and expectations. This enables private business colleges and universities administration offices to leverage the key aspects of improving customer satisfaction and building loyalty.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

Higher education of private colleges and universities got to screen advancing industry patterns closely to superior get it what current and future managers anticipate from their graduates, and how they of student's advantage. Instructing the center principles and hypotheses of a specific subject matter alone isn't sufficient to plan graduates for the changing computerized and visual worldwide work environment. This requires a college educational program that focuses on future-applicable abilities and results such as driving understudy choice. To attain this objective, colleges and universities ought to utilize instructing strategies such as the private colleges and universities.

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